

Thursday, November 14, 2019 4:56:44 AM

#	Query	Limiters/Expanders	Last Run Via	Results
S4	S1 AND S2	Limiters - Published Date: 19990101-20191231 Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL with Full Text	2,744
S3	S1 AND S2	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL with Full Text	2,849
S2	TI ((((step* OR stride*) N2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR length* OR width* OR frequenc* OR rate* OR rhythm* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr* OR count* OR number* OR distance* OR cadence*))) OR (((swing* OR stance* OR "single support" OR "double support") N2 (time* OR duration* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr*))) OR (((spatiotemporal OR "spatio-temporal") N2 (parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic*))) OR (((gait OR walk* OR ambulat*) N2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR cadence* OR pace* OR	Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Find all my search terms	Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL with Full Text	27,212

rhythm* OR volume* OR
bout* OR duration* OR
distance* OR intensit*
OR variabilit* OR
asymmetr* OR symmetr*
OR parameter* OR
feature* OR
characteristic* OR
assess* OR examin* OR
analys* OR batter* OR
measure* OR test*)))
OR AB ((((step* OR
stride*) N2 (speed OR
velocit* OR time* OR
length* OR width* OR
frequenc* OR rate* OR
rhythm* OR variabilit* OR
symmetr* OR asymmetr*
OR count* OR number*
OR distance* OR
cadence*)) OR (((swing*
OR stance* OR "single
support" OR "double
support") N2 (time* OR
duration* OR variabilit*
OR symmetr* OR
asymmetr*)) OR
(((spatiotemporal OR
"spatio-temporal") N2
(parameter* OR feature*
OR characteristic*)) OR
(((gait OR walk* OR
ambulat*) N2 (speed OR
velocit* OR time* OR
cadence* OR pace* OR
rhythm* OR volume* OR
bout* OR duration* OR
distance* OR intensit*
OR variabilit* OR
asymmetr* OR symmetr*
OR parameter* OR
feature* OR
characteristic* OR

	<p> assess* OR examin* OR analys* OR batter* OR measure* OR test*))) </p>			
S1	<p> ((MH "Pulmonary Disease, Chronic Obstructive+") OR (MH "Parkinson Disease") OR (MH "Parkinsonian Disorders+") OR (MH "Multiple Sclerosis+") OR (MH "Demyelinating Diseases+") OR (MH "Hip Fractures+")) OR TI ((((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*) N3 obstruct*) OR copd) OR (parkinson* OR "paralysis agitans") OR (((multipl* OR disseminated OR insular) N3 scleros*) OR "chariot disease" OR demyelinat*) OR ((hip* OR femur* OR femoral OR trochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant* OR subtrochant* OR intracapsular* OR extracapsular*) N5 fracture*)) OR AB (</p>	<p> Expanders - Apply equivalent subjects Search modes - Find all my search terms </p>	<p> Interface - EBSCOhost Research Databases Search Screen - Advanced Search Database - CINAHL with Full Text </p>	97,667
	<p> (((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*) N3 obstruct*) OR copd) OR (parkinson* OR "paralysis agitans") OR (((multipl* OR disseminated OR insular) N3 scleros*) OR "chariot disease" OR demyelinat*) OR ((hip* OR femur* OR </p>			

femoral OR trochant* OR
perthrochant* OR
intertrochant* OR
subtrochant* OR
intracapsular* OR
extracapsular*) N5
fracture*))